

KOMPYUTERLASHTIRILGAN TESTLARNING XUSUSIYATLARI

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XXI asr boshidan kompyuterlar ta’limni test qilishda keng qo’llanila boshlandi. Pedagogik innovatsiyalarda alohida yo’nalish - kompyuter testi paydo bo’ldi, unda testlarni taqdim etish, talabalar natijalarini baholash va ularga natijalarni berish shaxsiy kompyuter yordamida amalga oshiriladi. Test yaratish bosqichi texnologik jihatdan turli yo’llar bilan, shu jumladan kompyuterga bo’sh testlarni kiritish orqali davom etishi mumkin. Bugungi kunga kelib, kompyuter sinovlari bo’yicha ko’plab nashrlar mavjud, testlarni yaratish va taqdim etish uchun dasturiy ta’minot va vositalar ishlab chiqilgan. Test nima? Test-berilgan alternativ javoblardan to’g’risini tanlash shaklidagi nazorat topshirig’idir. O’quv fani bo’yicha tuziladigan nazorat testlari, boshqa o’quv topshiriqlariga o’xshab, to’rt xil elementlardan tarkib topadi; mazmun, maqsad, funksiya, metod.

Pedagogik testlar AQSH, Niderlandiya, Angliya, Turkiya, Janubiy Koreya, Yaponiya va boshqa ko’pgina mamlakatlarda keng rivoj topdi. Ushbu ro’yxatga asosan turmush darajasi yuqori bo’lgan mamlakatlar kirganligi tasodif emas.

Kompyuter testi - bu elektron kompyuterlardan foydalanish bilan bog’liq bo’lgan psixodiagnostik tadqiqotlarning (so’rovlar) yaqinda paydo bo’lgan sohasi. Kompyuter psixodiagnostikasining paydo bo’lishi axborot texnologiyalarining rivojlanishi bilan bog’liq. Mavzuga rag’batlantiruvchi materialni taqdim etish va natijalarni keyinchalik qayta ishlashni avtomatlashtirishga urinishlar 1930-yillardan boshlab amalga oshirildi. XX asr Ammo faqat 70-yillardan boshlab. kompyuter psixodiagnostikasining haqiqiy rivojlanishi shaxsiy kompyuterlarning paydo bo’lishi bilan bog’liq holda boshlanadi. 80-yillardan beri. kompyuter testlari keng miqyosda ishlab chiqilmoqda. Birinchidan, qanday qilib kompyuter versiyalari allaqachon ma’lum bo’sh texnikasi, va 90-yillarda. imkoniyatlarini hisobga olgan holda maxsus texnikalar sifatida zamonaviy texnologiya va bo’sh shaklda foydalanilmaydi, chunki ular makon va vaqtda o’zgarib turadigan murakkab rag’batlantiruvchi material, o’ziga xos tovush hamrohligi va boshqalar uchun mo’ljallangan. XXI asrning boshi tobora ko’proq sinov nazorati kompyuterga o’tkazilishi bilan ajralib turadi. Agar oldingi yillarda o’rganishning alohida bosqichlari avtomatlashtirilgan bo’lsa, masalan, material taqdimoti (taxistoskop

o'rniga kompyuterdan foydalanish juda qulay), ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash (ayniqsa, MMPI, 16PF, sotsiometriya kabi testlarni qayta ishlashda noqulay), natijalarni talqin qilish (Luscher testi), keyin hozirgi bosqich borgan sari tez-tez tashxis qo'yishgacha butun imtihonni o'z zimmasiga oladigan dasturlarni topishingiz mumkin, bu esa psixologga bo'lgan ehtiyojni minimal darajada kamaytiradi. Va bu o'zining ijobiy va salbiy tomonlariga ega.

Kompyuterlashtirilgan testlarning (KT) shubhasiz afzalliklari quyidagilardir: tez ishlash; yuqori tezlik va xatosiz ishlov berish; darhol natijalarni olish imkoniyati; barcha fanlar uchun standart test sharoitlarini ta'minlash; test jarayonini aniq nazorat qilish (savollarni o'tkazib yuborishning iloji yo'q, agar kerak bo'lsa, har bir javobning vaqtini belgilash mumkin, bu ayniqsa razvedka testlari uchun muhimdir); psixologni qo'shimcha o'zgaruvchi sifatida chiqarib tashlash imkoniyati (bu ekspertiza o'tkazishda alohida ahamiyatga ega); jarayonning ko'rinishi va qiziqarliligi (o'quv dasturlari uchun ayniqsa muhim bo'lgan rang, tovush, o'yin elementlari yordamida diqqatni qo'llab-quvvatlash); natijalarni oson arxivlash; testlarni bitta yakuniy talqin bilan batareyalarga (dasturiy ta'minot

paketlariga) birlashtirish imkoniyati; eksperimentatorning harakatchanligi (barcha asboblarni bitta disketada); ommaviy tadqiqotlar o'tkazish qobiliyati (masalan, Internet orqali).

Kompyuter testlarining kamchiliklari: murakkablik, mehnat zichligi va dasturiy ta'minotni ishlab chiqishning yuqori narxi; qimmat kompyuter uskunalarga bo'lgan ehtiyoj; sohada kompyuterlardan foydalanishning murakkabligi; KT bilan ishlash uchun sub'ektni maxsus tayyorlash zarurati; og'zaki bo'lmagan material bilan ishlashda qiyinchiliklar, proyektiv testlarni kompyuter shakliga o'tkazishning alohida qiyinligi; sinovchiga individual yondashishning yo'qligi (suhbat va kuzatishda olingan psixodiagnostik ma'lumotlarning bir qismini yo'qotish); ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash va talqin qilish bosqichlarining kechikishi (ushbu protseduralarning sifati butunlay dasturiy ta'minotni ishlab chiquvchilarga bog'liq). Ba'zi mavzularda kompyuter bilan o'zaro aloqada bo'lganda, "psixologik to'siq" yoki "ortiqcha ishonch" ta'siri paydo bo'lishi mumkin. Shu sababli, blank testlarining haqiqiyliги, ishonchligi va reprezentativligi to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlar avtomatik ravishda ularning kompyuterdagi hamkasblariga uzatilishi mumkin emas, bu esa testlarni yangi standartlashtirish zarurligiga olib keladi.

Kompyuter tomografiyasining kamchiliklari psixologlarni ulardan ehtiyot bo'lishga majbur qiladi. KT kam qo'llaniladi [klinik psixologiya](#) bu erda xatolik narxi juda yuqori [18].

L. S. Vygotskiy psixodiagnostikaning uchta darajasini aniqladi: simptomatik (simptomlarni aniqlash), etiologik (sabablarni aniqlash) va tipologik (shaxsning yaxlit, dinamik tasviri, uning asosida prognoz asoslanadi). Kompyuter psixodiagnostikasi bugungi kunda eng past darajada - simptomatik tashxis darajasida, sabablarni aniqlash va prognoz qilish uchun deyarli material bermaydi.

Ammo, aftidan, kompyuter tomografiyasining katta kelajagi bor, bu erda kompyuter psixodiagnostikasining sanab o'tilgan kamchiliklarining aksariyati albatta hal qilinadi. [yanada rivojlantirish](#) elektron texnologiyalar va psixodiagnostik texnologiyalarni takomillashtirish. Bunday optimizmning kaliti fan va amaliyotning kompyuter diagnostikasiga bo'lgan qiziqishi ortib bormoqda, uning arsenalida 1000 dan ortiq kompyuter tomografiyasi mavjud.

Agar biz hozirda mavjud bo'lgan KTni tasniflashga harakat qilsak, ularning quyidagi turlarini ajratib ko'rsatishimiz mumkin:

1. Tuzilishi bo'yicha

a) blank testlarning analoglari;

b) KTning o'zi.

2. Tekshirilganlar soni bo'yicha

a) KTni individual tekshirish;

b) guruh testining KT (mahalliy tarmoqqa ulangan kompyuterlarda bir xil materialni bir vaqtning o'zida taqdim etish uchun).

3. Sinovlarni avtomatlashtirish darajasi bo'yicha

a) so'rovning bir yoki bir necha bosqichlarini avtomatlashtirish;

b) barcha tekshiruvlarni avtomatlashtirish.

4. Vazifa bo'yicha

a) diagnostik KT;

b) o'qitish KT (simulyator testlari, rivojlanish dasturlari).

5. Qabul qiluvchi tomonidan

a) professional psixologik;

b) yarim professional;

v) noprofessional (o'yin-kulgi).

Professional kompyuter tomografiyasidan foydalanuvchi psixologdir, shuning uchun ular ixtisoslashtirilgan laboratoriyalar yoki kompyuter psixodiagnostika markazlari tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan (ular orasida

Moskvadagi Gumanitar texnologiyalar markazi, Imaton-M ZAO, VM klinik psixologiya laboratoriyasini eslatib o'tish kerak. Sankt-Peterburgdagi Bekhterev psixonevrologiya instituti va boshqalar). Ushbu testlar bir qator o'ziga xos xususiyatlarga ega: 1) arxiv (ma'lumotlar bazasi) mavjudligi; 2) natijalarning maxfiyligini ta'minlash uchun test yoki ma'lumotlar bazasiga kirish uchun parol mavjudligi; 3) grafiklarni (profillarni) qurish bilan professional atamalar, koefitsientlar yordamida natijalarni batafsil talqin qilish; 4) metodologiyani ishlab chiquvchilar to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlarning mavjudligi, haqiqiyli va ishonchliligi to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlar; [ma'lumotnoma materiallari](#) metodologiyaga asoslangan nazariy tamoyillar haqida. Yarim professional KT tegishli kasblar bo'yicha mutaxassislariga, masalan, o'qituvchilarga, HR menejerlariga qaratilgan. Bunday testlar ko'pincha maxsus lug'atdan foydalanmasdan qisqartirilgan talqin bilan ta'minlanadi va ularni o'rganish va ishlash oson. Ushbu darajadagi testlar mutaxassis bo'lmagan, psixologiyaga qiziqqan shaxsiy kompyuterning oddiy foydalanuvchisi uchun ham ishlab chiqilishi mumkin. Nihoyat, u ham bor [katta raqam](#) psixologik g'oyalarni ommalashtirish yoki dam olish maqsadlariga erishishga qaratilgan noprofessional kompyuter tomografiyasi.

Professional yoki yarim professional KT dan foydalanganda, xuddi shunday axloqiy tamoyillarga amal qilish kerak bo'sh testlar. Sinov natijalarini tarqatmaslik va fayllarni parol bilan himoya qilish muhim emas, ayniqsa kompyuterda bir nechta foydalanuvchi bo'lsa. Va asosiysi, "o'zingiz uchun but yaratmaslik". Esda tutingki, KT faqat vosita, faqat yordamchi va o'z qo'llash chegaralariga ega (uning bilimi professional psixolog charlatandan psixologiyadan farq qiladi).

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